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24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

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UNIFood2021 Conference

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The word of welcome

Dear colleagues,

We would like to welcome you to the **2nd UNIFood International Conference –UNIFood2021**. We hope that this gathering will engage not only academics, but also the stakeholders from all the relevant industries and business sectors, serving as a meeting point and a platform for proliferation of new ideas and development of new partnerships.

The first UNIFood conference, organized as national, was established 2018. year as one of the events in honor of the **210th Anniversary** celebration of the **University of Belgrade** that ranked at Shanghai list on 35th place for the 2017 year in subject *Food Science and Technology*. The University of Belgrade has been recognized as a leading international scientific institution by LERU when it was selected to be a member of CE7, an informal network of seven Central and Eastern European universities collaborating with LERU on key research and education challenges. Furthermore, University of Belgrade joined European University Alliance Circle U. Following the European Commission's launch of the European Universities initiative, a group of research-intensive universities has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the intention of establishing a new university alliance: Aarhus University, Humboldt University of Berlin, King's College London, UC Louvain, University of Belgrade, University of Oslo and Université de Paris.

We are pleased that you have decided to take part in this mutual conversation, where many will present their recent work, through poster sessions, oral communications or simply by asking questions. One of the goals of this Conference is cooperation between academia and food industry. Food scientists, technologists, researchers, nutritionists, engineers and entrepreneurs will exchange their knowledge about the latest advances in all aspects of food production, processing, sustainability, safety and security, nutrition and health, hi-tech equipment, ethics and knowledge transfer supporting environment. At this meeting, over 200 participants from 23 countries will take part.

Belgrade, one of the oldest city in the Europe, always young, at the confluence of the Sava and Danube rivers, will be your host. At the confluence of new ideas and experiences we again wish you a warm welcome.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić

*President of the Scientific Committee
of UNIFood2021*

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović

Rector of the University of Belgrade

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE BILBERRY-BASED JUICES

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The consumption of superfruit juices has risen globally. Namely, the consumption of fresh raw and commercially available bilberry juices is becoming a part of a healthy lifestyle due to potential health benefits derived from biological effects of naturally occurring phenolics contained in berries. Moreover, assessing the quality and safety of food products, especially the ones considered as health beneficial is of great importance.

The aim of this study was to examine total phenolic content (TPC), anthocyanin content, antioxidant activities as well as the content of elements, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) and patulin of eight commercially available bilberry-based juices. TPC was determined using Folin-Ciocalteu method, total monomeric anthocyanin content by the pH differential method while *in vitro* antioxidant activity by DPPH radical assay. The HPLC methods were employed in quantification of HMF and patulin. Fifteen elements were analyzed using ICP-MS method (nutritionally important minerals were not included).

TPC was up to 2861.5 mg GAE/L while total monomeric anthocyanin content was up to 452.27 mg/L cyanidin-3-glucoside equivalents in the analyzed samples. High *in vitro* antioxidant capacities were confirmed in the samples with high TPC and total monomeric anthocyanins with a statistically significant correlation observed between TPC and antioxidant activity. The amount of HMF, a quality indicator, ranged between 0.4 mg/L and 17.9 mg/L in the analyzed juices, meeting the regulation. A mycotoxin patulin was quantified in only one sample, with the content below maximum regulated level (50 µg/kg, European Commission) indicating the use of good quality raw material in juice manufacture. Analysis showed that low amounts of lead were found in two juice samples, but below allowable level. Aluminum and barium were quantified in all samples, boron and cobalt were determined in three samples, while ten elements were not detected.

The results of this study are important to estimate the overall benefits and risks of consumption of commercially available bilberry-based juices.

Keywords: bilberry, juice, phenolic compounds, quality